

Micro-precipitation Equipment for the Use of Potassium Trithiocarbonate as the Cation-precipitant

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The overall superiority of potassium trithiocarbonate reagent (Johri, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1958, **17B**, 333; 1959, **18B**, 430) over hydrogen sulphide and thioacetamide (Blomendal and Veer Kamp, *Chem. Weekbl.*, 1953, **49**, 147; Lehrman and Schneider, *J Chem. Ed.*, 1955, **32**, 474) as cation-precipitant has made possible to extend its application to micro-analysis with great advantages.

Treatment of test solutions in micro-analysis with hydrogen sulphide obtained from a U-tube micro-generator (Sorum, "Introduction to Semimicro Analysis") fitted with a jet delivery tube and a spring-clip has proved far from satisfactory. Besides the undue leakage of the gas and the contamination of laboratory atmosphere, frequent blocking of the jet delivery-tube of the generator results due to the capillary suction of a test solution and its consequent precipitation within the jet. To avoid this, a high pressure ejection of the gas from the jet becomes necessary before it is either inserted into the test solution or withdrawn from it. This results in the leakage of the gas in a greater degree and also in the sputtering of the test solution.

On the other hand, while using potassium trithiocarbonate reagent and the 'micro-precipitation equipment', the above noted difficulties are successfully overcome. As an additional advantage, the products of precipitation are obtained in highly coagulated form, necessitating only minimum centrifuging in the case of such cations of which the products of precipitation tend to become colloidal. Cadmium is prominent in this respect, as in low concentration its sulphide tends to become colloidal. Furthermore, the use of potassium trithiocarbonate makes possible the application of the new technique, called "precipitation from homogeneous solution". Under this technique the precipitating agent is not added as such, but is generated within the solution by a chemical reaction. In the case of the thiocarbonate reagent, it is the thiocarbonic acid or hydrogen sulphide, which is generated, depending on the pH at a stage.

Equipment and Procedure

This apparatus, as represented in Fig 1, has been made with quick-fit joints out of pyrex parts. It is meant to carry out precipitation of minute quantities of inorganic materials

as sulphides or thiocarbonates, depending on the pH of the test solutions. This will accomplish the clean separation of the cations without causing any sputtering or leakage of any toxic gas. The conical enclosure forms the main body of the set-up in which a micro-beaker (M) or a centrifuge-tube (T) containing the test solution is lodged firmly in position with the help of glass stopper ($Fig. 1a$) or a rubber cork ($Fig. 1b$) holding the tube.

FIG. 1.

The dropping funnel (B), provided with a long narrow stem and a stop cock, holds nearly $0.25N$ - HCl . The second dropping funnel (R) is meant to deliver in drops the trithiocarbonate reagent to a test solution for precipitation. The part (A) is charged with a dilute solution of KOH through which any liberated hydrogen sulphide bubbles and is trapped, the residual gas being completely drawn out of (F) by connecting (C) to a filter pump while stopper (S) is slightly loosened in the end to admit air from below. This is done before withdrawing the micro-beaker or the centrifuge tube after each precipitation. While adding the thiocarbonate reagent to a test-solution, the end of the jet (J_1) is moved by rotating (H_1) so as to touch the side of the microbeaker or the centrifuge tube. Same procedure is adopted when the acid from (B) is added for the subsequent treatment of group II metal sulphides. A protective layer of liquid paraffin, kept over the reagent in funnel (R) maintains its purity. When precipitation with the thiocarbonate reagent is complete, the stopper of the bulb (A) is connected to suction line (filter pump) and the stopper (S) carrying the micro-beaker or the rubber cork holding the centrifuge tube is taken out to check the pH of the test solution with the help of methyl violet indicator paper. The whole apparatus rests at the same height and clamped vertically, as shown in $Fig. 1$. The bulb (A) is periodically emptied and after washing with water it is recharged with a fresh dilute solution of KOH . Potassium hydrogen sulphide collected from (A) can be subsequently utilised in the preparation of the trithiocarbonate reagent.

4,5,8-Trihydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone (*Helminthosporin*) (III).—The above benzoylbenzoic acid (XIII) (0.9 g.) was cyclised and simultaneously demethylated using sulphuric acid-boric acid mixture as in the earlier case. The anthraquinone crystallised from pyridine as flat, maroon needles with a bronze lustre, m.p. 226-27°, yield, 0.04 g. (Found: C, 66.7; H, 4.6. $C_{15}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 66.7; H, 3.7%). It was identical with a sample of natural helminthosporin. λ_{max}^{MeOH} (log ϵ) for synthetic helminthosporin: 231 (4.52), 253 (4.15), 287 (3.80), 320 (2.91) and 490 m μ . (4.10); for natural helminthosporin: 230 (4.64), 254 (4.30), 287 (3.93), 320 (2.96) and 490 m μ (4.09).

Its triacetate was prepared using acetic anhydride and sulphuric acid (conc.) and it crystallised from a mixture of glacial acetic acid and acetic anhydride as pale yellow needles, m.p. 223-24°, agreeing with the earlier record (Raistrick *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

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